

How Important is Spatial Invariance Symmetry to Quantum Mechanics? Part III

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 30, 2024

In parts I and II, we tried to argue that the quantum mechanical free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ emerges from considerations of spatial invariance in classical probability equations. In particular, we considered the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem and its associated conservation of probability, i.e. $1 = P_{\text{reflected}} + P_{\text{refracted}}$. We suggested that the probability conservation equation does not explicitly display an x dependent equation and suggested there should exist such an equation(s) such that they collapse to the x -independent one (probability conservation)

. In Part II, we considered the expression for spatial probability $P(x)dx = dx/L$ for a free particle and argued that $1/L$ (where L is length) may be written as AA (positivity). We suggested again that there should exist x dependent expressions which collapse to AA . We suggested $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$.

In this note, we first suggest that an x -dependent equation should exist in order to demonstrate conservation of momentum through d/dx which is a translational operator. Secondly, we extend these ideas to the $E = p^2/2m$ and $E = p^2/c^2 + m^2c^4$. We suggest that even though $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution of $E = p^2/2m$ with $p \rightarrow -i\hbar d/dx$, the more fundamental equation is $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ which is associated with momentum conservation. In other words, $E = p^2/2m$ may be considered to be a scalar equation holding at any x due to spatial invariance. This implies that one seek a linear x dependent equation displaying momentum conservation or $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$.

We extend these ideas to special relativity and suggest this implies the Klein-Gordon equation should be linearized, i.e. there should be an equation linear in d/dx which is associated with the conserved quantity momentum. As in Parts I and II, extra physics emerges when one considers x -explicit equations which combine to create an equation (in this case the Klein-Gordon) which displays less information. In particular, Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation and found information about spin $1/2$ and antimatter for negative E values.

Spatial Invariance

In Part I and II, we suggested that if spatial invariance exists, and there also exists an equation which does not explicitly display x (because there is x invariance), then there should exist x dependent equations or expressions which combine to create this x independent expression. We found, by examining two examples, that extra physical information emerges through these x -dependent equations, in particular free particle quantum mechanics.

In Part I, we considered one dimensional reflection-refraction and noted that a probability conservation equation, which applies immediately, does not contain x . In particular:

$$1 = P_{\text{reflected}} + P_{\text{refracted}} \rightarrow AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2 \quad ((1))$$

where A/c = incident flux divided by the speed of light c in a vacuum or incident probability, where A designates positivity. B and C are the reflected and refracted fluxes and c_2 the refracted speed. $\text{flux}/c = \text{probability}$.

No x appears in ((1)) and one has two unknowns B and C , if A is considered known. We also note that $E=pc$ for a photon, so $1/c_i = p_i/E$ with E being the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photon. Following the suggested principle that there should exist x -dependent equations linked with translational invariance, we suggested a function which was continuous at x_1 (the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction) together with its first derivative. The first derivative, however, could yield p_i and so this suggests $\exp(ipx)$ for a translationally invariant type of function. One may thus write:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C \exp(-ip_2x) \quad ((2a)) \text{ and } A\exp(ipx) - B\exp(-ipx) = C_2 \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((2b))$$

at $x=x_1$

Taking the complex conjugate of ((2a)) and multiplying by ((2b)) yields ((1))

Thus, one obtains the two required equations needed to solve for two unknowns as well as the physics associated with $\exp(ipx)$.

In Part II, we considered $P(x)dx=dx/L$ where L is length, and suggested that $1/L=A$ for positivity. If one is required to have two x -dependent expressions which collapse to A , one may suggest: $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ and $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}$. Again, quantum mechanics emerges.

The Case of Momentum Conservation

We suggest that there is an added feature linked with the x -dependent equations listed above, namely momentum conservation. $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$, where d/dx is the translational operator. As a result, d/dx shows how the particle moves in space according to the conserved quantity p , which is already known to be conserved from Newtonian mechanics.

In particular, we consider a free particle and the two features:

$$\text{Momentum is } p \text{ at any } x \text{ and } E=pp/2m \text{ at any } x \quad ((3))$$

In quantum mechanics texts, one sometimes sees $E=pp/2m$ with $p \rightarrow -i\hbar/dx$ and the emergence of $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution of this equation (time-independent Schrodinger equation with $V(x)=0$). We suggest, however, that the idea of momentum is more important because it is always conserved. In other words, in addition, to the time-independent Schrodinger equation for a free particle, there is also the equation:

$$-i\hbar/dx W = p W \quad \text{where } W = \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

There is no reason to have two equations which yield $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that ((4)) is the more fundamental for the reason of momentum conservation. We also suggest that $E=pp/2m$ exists as a scalar equation at any x point, so there is spatial invariance. Instead of only using $P(x)dx=dx/L$ to derive $\exp(ipx)$, we suggest that one could, in principle, also include $E=pp/2m$ ((5)). In this case, one requires x expressions which collapse to ((5)), but also carry momentum

information. Momentum is conserved in space. Thus, $\exp(i f(p,x)/\sqrt{L})$ and $\exp(-i f(p,x)/\sqrt{L})$ multiply together to yield $1/L$, but ((5)) requires momentum which is a conserved quantity in space. If $\exp(i f(p,x))$ were an eigenfunction, so to speak, of d/dx the translational operator, then one would have both $P(x)dx=d/L$ and $E=pp/2m$ described by a two x -dependent expressions. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$.

We suggest extending these ideas to the special relativistic case.

Special Relativity

$$EE = pcpc + momocccc \quad ((6))$$

is the free particle energy-momentum expression in special relativity. We suggest that like:

$$E - pp/2m \rightarrow -id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

one should be able to consider ((6)) as a scalar equation which holds at any x and seek two x -dependent expressions which combine to create ((6)). This suggests a linearization of ((6)) which explicitly demonstrates x and contains momentum conservation. In other words, if p appears in the linearization, one might consider $\exp(ipx)$ again.

As Dirac showed, this linearization process is possible if one uses 4×4 matrices and again $\exp(ipx)$ appears with $p \rightarrow -id/dx$, but now the matrices themselves have vector eigenfunctions which are associated with two kinds of new physics, spin and antimatter.

Thus, we suggest that although one may take ((6)) and use $E \rightarrow id/dt$ partial and $p \rightarrow -id/dx$ and convert ((6)) into a differential equation, called the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$-d/dt d/dt \text{ partial } W(x,t) = -d/dx d/dx W(x,t) + momo W(x,t) \text{ with } c=1 \quad ((8))$$

one may also consider ((6)) to be a scalar equation and seek a linear form which shows x explicitly and momentum conservation through $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, we suggest that the Dirac linearization process is a process of explicitly demonstrating spatial translational invariance, like the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem and the linearization of $P(x)dx=d/L$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have suggested in Part I and II that if a problem exhibits spatial translational invariance, there should exist explicit x dependent equations or expressions, directly linked with momentum conservation (through the translational operator d/dx) which combine to yield an x -independent equation (because of x invariance). These ideas were applied in Part I and II to one dimensional reflection-refraction and $P(x)dx=d/L$ (where L is length) and $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle quantum wavefunction emerged.

Here we suggest that $E=pp/2m$ may be used together with $P(x)dx=d/L$ to also demonstrate the emergence of $\exp(ipx)$. In this case, we treat $E=pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic) as a scalar equation and note that $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ with eigenvalue p . Thus, we suggest that for

a free particle, the essential equation is $-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. This establishes $p \rightarrow -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}$ which may later be used in $E = \frac{p^2}{2m}$.

Extending these ideas to special relativity, we take $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4$ to be a scalar equation which holds at any x due to spatial translational invariance. This suggests that one requires two x dependent equations which combine to yield (A) . Each linear equation should also be linked with momentum conservation, i.e. one expects a linear p which may be obtained from $\exp(ipx)$ using $-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}$, which in fact occurs. This linearization, already performed by Dirac, however, leads to the emergence of 4×4 matrices which lead to the physical notions of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and antimatter (if one allows for $-E$ solutions as well as E).